

Earth Camera Network with DAS systems for non-invasive wildlife migration datasets and inter species communication.

Dr Bheemaiah Anil K , Synergy Robotics , Seattle WA 98125 USA.

Introduction.

Wyzer, the human in the loop M.L learning program, has new data sets from Wyze V2 and V3 cameras used in wildlife observation apart from Landslide detection.

In a previous study using YouTube videos of landslides projected on a wall, Wyze V3 based pixel motion detection hardware had achieved a 100% accuracy in detection of landslides.

In this study, Wyze Cam v.3 is used with motion detection for animal observation logs, as data sets for data mining usable information like migration patterns, conservation monitoring, species identification with cam AI and animal tracking in lieu of invasive collaring techniques.

A combination of distributed acoustic sensing on buried fiber networks , coupled with distributed camera sensing, proves a non-invasive approach to conservation and the unnecessariness of traditional measures like collaring and radio collars.

Democratization of Speech, inter-species communication.

Hunters have traditionally used deer calls in hunting techniques. In a similar experiment, the author used a remote Wyze V3 camera for remote inter species communication with deer vocalizations.

An example of the logs is included below.

Deer vocalizations are well documented in literature. The automated data mining of DAS and DVS systems can be used to create interactive inter species vocalization systems as UI/UX enabling a large event calculus based system like RAVATTT or IFTTT, with actions like automated wildlife gates, food robotics, warning systems, information systems for wildlife, in wildlife vocalizations.

The Buddhist Economy and meta ethics.

The deer chitta, coupled with the bodhi chitta of arborio dendrology, are central tenets in Buddhist mainstream thought. The existence of the Buddhist Economy and the metaethics of a neo Pagan and Buddhist culture in the context of the Indian Subcontinent, revives ancient heritage of inter species

communication and wildlife conflict resolution in the importance and the higher status of wildlife in the context of pre and post industrialized societies.

With the example of the IIT Madras campus, internationalization and increased multinational investments have brought more resources to conservation efforts, needing democratization of existing subterranean fiber optic networks and earth cams to a inter species conversational UI/UX and event calculus for robotics. Similarly the monkey chitta, though criticized in mainstream Buddhist cultures has its place as a revered bardo in Hinduism, in the context of Vaanars and the west in the context of Sasquatch and Simian Yeti and other species of non-human people.

In the context of a river being recognized legally as a person, dolphins as persons, elephants may soon be recognized as a person, along with several non-human species, the strong animal rights advocacy.

Antelopes of IIT Madras.

Black Bucks are a species of antelopes omnipresent in the Indian Subcontinent with a threatened status, recently revived by the Indian Governments DNR and Department of the interiors efforts at conservation, revered in mainstream Indian religions as on with the forester and Lord, traditional cultures lean on strong arbero dendrological roots with restorative ecology, a part of the fabric of society, in practiced tree transplantation, arboretums(manu vana), genetic conservatories(moola vana) and food plots and sacred groves (devara vana).

The creation of food plots and planting of indigenous food chain plants for the Black Buck is underway as prairie restoration measures.¹

Biologists track antelope hotspots, with reforestation of grasses replacing invasive prosopis.¹

Increased use of AI models, ecological datasets and robotic transplantation like ATV Utility based tree spades and the Volvo FMX 450 Transplant are called for.

Chital of IIT Madras.

Chital or Spotted Deer are a species of deer found in the Indian Subcontinent similar in biomarking to several species found around the world. They are not threatened and abound the IIT Madras campus. The latest census bounds their population at 150 chital and 50 Black Buck.²

Conservation of Caribou in Canada.

Boreal caribou are a geographically important species, classified as critically endangered and restored as a successful chapter in conservation history by primarily indigenous forces. The restoration lends to an indigenous version of restorative ecology without picture perfect wildlife head starting. The emphasis is on native or ethnobiological sources of intuitive and direct knowledge of plants and their restoration mush by traditional ways, in line with akira miyawakis philosophy of restoration.

The efforts wed technology and scientific practices in active anti poaching patrols and food plot management.

In Comparison with iit madras where similar efforts to end wildlife human conflicts, restore ecology had only just begun missing a recognition of native intelligence and ethnobotany. In a land rife with conflicts where the indigenous people: their culture and floral faunal wealth have been completely wiped out even the land grant is not yet acknowledged the languages are extinct with a conservation program rudimentary in its sources and barely successful. The dwindling population may remain stable or recover as hope in the form of autonomous navigation products like comma.ai raises moral i. The hope that human and wildlife lives are saved in safer automobiles.

Interspecies Communication.

Caribou calls.

Methods.

Methods as a SciPi Contest Project with LORA, Pi4, and Wyze V3/V2 Cameras for Automated Data Gathering and Archival

The goal of this project is to develop a system that utilizes LORA, Pi4, and Wyze V3/V2 cameras for movement detection and sound activation, automated data gathering, and archival on the Wyze cloud. The system also includes optional archiving on IPFS, Azure, or AWS for datamining purposes. The following steps outline the methods used in the project:

1. Setup the Hardware: The first step is to set up the hardware, which includes the Pi4, LORA, and Wyze V3/V2 cameras. The Pi4 is connected to the LORA module, which is used for long-range communication. The Wyze V3/V2 cameras are connected to the Pi4 via USB.
2. Configure the Wyze Cameras: The Wyze cameras are configured to detect movement and sound using their built-in sensors. The cameras are also set up to upload the recorded data to the Wyze cloud.
3. Configure the Pi4: The Pi4 is configured to receive data from the Wyze cameras and LORA module. The Pi4 is also configured to analyze the data received and send it to the Wyze cloud for archival purposes.
4. Implement the Data Gathering and Archival System: The system is designed to gather data from the Wyze cameras and LORA module when motion or sound is detected. The data is then analyzed and sent to the Wyze cloud for archival purposes. Optional archiving on IPFS, Azure, or AWS is also implemented for datamining purposes.

5. **Test the System:** The system is tested to ensure that it is functioning as intended. The Wyze cameras and LORA module are tested to ensure that they are properly detecting motion and sound. The data gathered is also analyzed to ensure that it is accurate and complete.

In summary, the project uses LORA, Pi4, and Wyze V3/V2 cameras for movement detection and sound activation, automated data gathering, and archival on the Wyze cloud. The system also includes optional archiving on IPFS, Azure, or AWS for datamining purposes. The methods used in the project include setting up the hardware, configuring the Wyze cameras and Pi4, implementing the data gathering and archival system, and testing the system.

Machine Learning Models for Data Mining

Data mining is the process of discovering patterns and insights in large datasets. Machine learning has become an essential tool for data mining, providing algorithms and techniques for uncovering hidden patterns in complex datasets. In this section, we will discuss some of the most commonly used machine learning models for data mining.

Recurrent Convolutional Neural Networks (R-CNNs)

R-CNNs are a type of neural network that are particularly useful for processing sequential data, such as time-series data or natural language data. R-CNNs are capable of learning long-term dependencies between inputs, making them well-suited for tasks such as predicting stock prices or classifying text data.

Support Vector Machines (SVMs)/ Quantum SVMs

SVMs are a type of supervised learning algorithm that can be used for classification and regression tasks. SVMs are particularly useful for tasks such as image classification, text classification, and time-series analysis. SVMs work by finding the hyperplane that maximizes the margin between different classes, making them effective at handling non-linear decision boundaries.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)

CNNs are a type of neural network that are particularly useful for processing image data. CNNs are capable of learning features at multiple scales, allowing them to identify patterns in images regardless of their location or size. CNNs have been used in a wide range of applications, including image recognition, object detection, and facial recognition.

Random Forests

Random Forests are a type of ensemble learning algorithm that combine multiple decision trees to make more accurate predictions. Random Forests can be used for classification and regression tasks, making them useful for a wide range of data mining applications. Random Forests are particularly effective at handling noisy data and missing values.

Hidden Markov Models (HMMs)

HMMs are a type of probabilistic model that are particularly useful for modeling sequential data. HMMs are commonly used for tasks such as speech recognition, handwriting recognition, and natural language processing. HMMs work by modeling the probability of transitioning between different states, making them effective at modeling complex patterns in sequential data.

Long Short-Term Memory Networks (LSTMs)

LSTMs are a type of RNN that are particularly useful for processing long sequences of data. LSTMs are capable of learning long-term dependencies between inputs, making them well-suited for tasks such as language modeling and speech recognition. LSTMs are particularly effective at handling the problem of vanishing gradients, which can occur when training RNNs on long sequences of data.

AI Business Case for Inter-Species Communication and Conservation in the Caribou Industry

The use of AI technology to understand and communicate with different species provides numerous benefits for the conservation economy, job creation, food plot and Miyawaki landscaping, biodiversity conservation, and the development of event-driven robotics.

Conservation Economy

Caribou populations are a critical component of the conservation economy, as they play a vital role in maintaining the health and diversity of ecosystems. The use of AI technology to understand and communicate with caribou can provide valuable insights into their behavior, migration patterns, and habitat requirements. This information can be used to develop conservation strategies that protect caribou populations and promote biodiversity.

Job Creation

The development of AI technology for inter-species communication and conservation creates new job opportunities in the caribou industry. For example, individuals with expertise in AI, data analysis, and wildlife biology can work together to develop and implement conservation strategies that protect

caribou populations. Additionally, the development of smart homes and pet robotics creates new job opportunities in the technology industry.

Food Plot and Miyawaki Landscaping

The use of AI technology to understand and communicate with caribou can also inform food plot and Miyawaki landscaping practices. By understanding caribou's dietary needs and habitat requirements, conservationists and landowners can create more effective food plots and Miyawaki landscapes that promote biodiversity and provide important habitat for caribou and other species.

Biodiversity Conservation

AI technology can play a critical role in the conservation of biodiversity. By understanding and communicating with caribou, conservationists can develop conservation strategies that promote the health and diversity of ecosystems. This can include the development of habitat corridors, restoration of degraded landscapes, and protection of important habitats.

Medicinal and Ethno Botany

AI technology can also inform medicinal and ethno botany practices. By understanding the interactions between caribou and their environment, conservationists and traditional healers can identify important medicinal plants and develop sustainable harvesting practices that protect caribou populations and promote biodiversity.

Event-Driven Robotics

Finally, the use of event-driven robotics triggered by caribou calls can provide valuable information on caribou behavior and migration patterns. By collecting data on caribou movements and behavior, conservationists can develop more effective conservation strategies and improve our understanding of caribou populations.

Proposal for a Public Caribou Utterance Dataset and Trained Utterance Models

Introduction

Caribou vocalizations are a key component of their social behavior and communication. The development of a public dataset of caribou utterances and trained utterance models can provide valuable insights into their behavior, migration patterns, and habitat requirements. This information can be used to develop conservation strategies that protect caribou populations and promote biodiversity.

Dataset Creation

The creation of a caribou utterance dataset would involve the following steps:

1. **Audio Collection:** Audio recordings of caribou vocalizations would need to be collected in the field. This can be done using microphones placed at strategic locations in caribou habitats or by using drones to capture audio recordings from above.
2. **Annotation:** Once audio recordings are collected, they will need to be annotated to identify the different types of caribou vocalizations. This can be done using existing knowledge of caribou vocalizations or by using machine learning algorithms to automatically classify utterances.
3. **Curation:** The annotated audio recordings will need to be curated and organized into a publicly available dataset that can be accessed and analyzed by researchers and conservationists.

Trained Utterance Models

Once a caribou utterance dataset is created, trained utterance models can be developed to analyze the data. This can involve the use of machine learning algorithms such as deep neural networks or hidden Markov models. These models can be trained to classify different types of caribou vocalizations, identify patterns in migration behavior, and even predict the health and well-being of caribou populations.

Benefits of a Public Caribou Utterance Dataset and Trained Utterance Models

The development of a public caribou utterance dataset and trained utterance models would provide numerous benefits for conservationists and researchers working in the caribou industry. Some of the potential benefits include:

1. Improved understanding of caribou behavior and migration patterns.
2. Development of more effective conservation strategies that protect caribou populations and promote biodiversity.
3. Identification of potential threats to caribou populations, such as habitat fragmentation or human disturbance.
4. Creation of new job opportunities in the technology and conservation industries.
5. Potential for collaboration and knowledge sharing among researchers and conservationists.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the creation of a public caribou utterance dataset and trained utterance models has the potential to provide valuable insights into the behavior and communication of caribou populations. This information can be used to develop more effective conservation strategies and promote biodiversity conservation in the caribou industry.

Identifying Optimal Sites for Arctic Caribou Utterance Data Collection in B.C Canada

The optimal sites for collecting arctic caribou utterance data using Wyze cameras in B.C Canada would be those areas that are known to be frequented by caribou populations. These areas are typically characterized by a mix of open tundra and shrub habitats, and are often located near water sources such as rivers and lakes.

One potential site for caribou utterance data collection using Wyze cameras is in the Peel Watershed region of northern B.C. This region is known to support a large and diverse population of caribou, and is characterized by extensive wetlands and rivers that are used by caribou for migration and foraging.

Another potential site for caribou utterance data collection using Wyze cameras is in the Muskwa-Kechika Management Area in northeastern B.C. This area is characterized by high alpine meadows and mountainous terrain, and is known to support large herds of mountain caribou.

Data Collection Plan

To gather caribou utterance data using Wyze cameras, a specific plan of number of hours of observation at different sites can be developed. This plan can involve both stationary and mobile observations, using both Wyze cameras and ATVs.

Stationary observations can be conducted by placing Wyze cameras in strategic locations such as near watering holes or on high ground overlooking caribou migration routes. These cameras can be set to record for a specified period of time each day, and the data can then be collected and analyzed.

Mobile observations can be conducted using ATVs equipped with cameras and microphones. These observations can be conducted along known caribou migration routes, and can be used to collect data on caribou vocalizations and behavior in different habitats.

A specific plan for data collection could involve the following:

1. Peel Watershed region: 200 hours of stationary observations using Wyze cameras at strategic locations such as near watering holes and migration routes, and 50 hours of mobile observations using ATVs equipped with cameras and microphones.
2. Muskwa-Kechika Management Area: 150 hours of stationary observations using Wyze cameras at strategic locations such as high ground overlooking caribou migration routes, and 100 hours of mobile observations using ATVs equipped with cameras and microphones.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the optimal sites for collecting arctic caribou utterance data using Wyze cameras in B.C Canada are those areas that are known to be frequented by caribou populations. A specific plan for data collection can involve both stationary and mobile observations using both Wyze cameras and ATVs. The

data collected from these observations can provide valuable insights into caribou behavior and communication, and can be used to develop more effective conservation strategies for caribou populations.

Future Work and Speculation

There are several potential areas for future work and development related to the study of arctic caribou and their conservation. Some potential areas for future work and speculation include:

1. **Airlifting of caribou:** As caribou populations continue to decline due to habitat loss and other factors, there may come a point where it becomes necessary to physically transport caribou to new habitats or safe havens. One potential method for doing this is through airlifting, using helicopters or other aircraft to transport caribou to new locations.
2. **Safe havens for reproduction:** Another potential area for future work is the development of safe havens for caribou reproduction. These safe havens could be located in remote areas with limited human activity, and could be designed to provide ideal habitat and conditions for caribou to mate and give birth to healthy offspring.
3. **Miyawaki pens:** Miyawaki pens are a type of wildlife enclosure that is designed to mimic natural habitats and provide ideal conditions for animal reproduction and conservation. These pens could be used to house caribou populations in areas where natural habitats have been degraded or destroyed, providing a safe and secure environment for caribou to thrive.
4. **Scientific consulting:** As the study of arctic caribou and their conservation becomes increasingly important, there may be a growing demand for scientific consulting services. These services could provide advice and expertise on a range of topics, including caribou behavior, habitat restoration, and conservation strategies.

While these potential areas for future work and development are largely speculative, they highlight the importance of continued research and innovation in the field of arctic caribou conservation. By working together and exploring new ideas and approaches, we can help to ensure that these iconic and important animals continue to thrive in the years to come.

References.

1. **Animal Call Understanding:**
 - Farina, A. (2015). *Acoustic ecology of animals*. Elsevier.
 - Marler, P. (1991). *The instinct to learn*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

- Bee, M. A., & Swanson, E. M. (2007). Auditory masking of anuran advertisement calls by road traffic noise. *Animal Behaviour*, 74(6), 1765-1776.
2. Caribou Call Research:
- Latham, A. D. M., Latham, M. C., & McCowan, B. (2013). Vocal ontogeny in caribou (*Rangifer tarandus*). *Journal of Mammalogy*, 94(4), 889-900.
 - Kirsch, P., Adams, L. G., & Côté, S. D. (2007). Linking movement and reproductive history of female caribou reveals the importance of conservation in areas with high road density. *Biological Conservation*, 138(3-4), 475-488.
 - LeBlanc, M. J., Brodeur, V., Dussault, C., & Côté, S. D. (2015). Effects of human disturbance on use of a late-successional forest ecosystem by caribou during calving season. *Ecosphere*, 6(2), 1-16.
3. Machine Learning Research:
- Goodfellow, I., Bengio, Y., & Courville, A. (2016). *Deep Learning*. MIT Press.
 - Jordan, M. I., & Mitchell, T. M. (2015). Machine learning: Trends, perspectives, and prospects. *Science*, 349(6245), 255-260.
 - Hastie, T., Tibshirani, R., & Friedman, J. (2009). *The elements of statistical learning: Data mining, inference, and prediction*. Springer Science & Business Media.
4. Caribou Observation:
- Ray, J. C., Douglas, D. C., & Giroux, M. A. (2018). Wildlife conservation and management in the Canadian Arctic: progress and challenges. *Environmental Reviews*, 26(1), 55-68.
 - Fryxell, J. M., & Sinclair, A. R. (1988). Causes and consequences of migration by large herbivores. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 3(9), 237-241.
 - Whitten, K. R. (2011). Caribou in the Canadian Arctic: changing landscapes, shifting values. *Environmental Reviews*, 19(S1), 171-187.
 - Oppili, P. & Venugopal, V. Big boost to blackbuck conservation at IIT-M. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/tamil-nadu/big-boost-to-blackbuck-conservation-at-iit-m/article5157291.ece> (2013).
 - Gautham, K. IIT-Madras loses a sixth of spotted deer in six months. *Times Of India* <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/chennai/chennai-iit-madras-loses-a-sixth-of-spotted-deer-in-six-months/articleshow/93122595.cms> (2022).